

THE GENRE OF THE ACADEMIC DISCOURSE

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Abstract:

This research paper has explored that the pedagogical discourse includes the whole field of the pedagogical activity and its social relations. In the pedagogical discourse the teacher's activity and the teaching process' social participants and the tools are the object of the research. The genre of academic discourse can be the important part of the communication during the pedagogical process and it impacts on the outcomes of the teaching and learning.

Key words: Genre, academic discourse, micro genres, participants, communicative situations.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/d24j7648>

1.Introduction. In modern linguistics there are several approaches to the speech genres. The scholar M.M.Bakhtin is the researcher of the speech genres stated that the genre is the stable type of the utterance [2]. The classification of the genres is based on the communicative intention of the linguistic personality. The genre of the academic discourse is commonly oral and written. Accordingly, there are many micro genres in the academic discourse such as the educational –didactic genre for example, books, teaching manuals, handouts ant etc.; the educational –academic genre such as the control work, the school essay, report, assignment, master dissertation and etc.; -educational –academic genre for gaining and improving the knowledge such as class work, homework, lecture and etc.; - scientific –academic genre such as the scientific publications, annotation, critique, dissertation and etc. The secondary written micro genres are the syllabus, the program of the discipline. The academic discourse can be illustrated by these above-mentioned genres because all of them are written in the academic language which is understandable to the addressee - the academic personality of the academic sphere. A lesson, a lecture, a conference report, a presentation, a seminar, a discussion, debate can be characterized the oral type of the genre of the academic discourse.

2.Main part. The study of the written and spoken discourse have been researches by many scholars in the last decades. It was the basis for the creation of the genre schools. Three Genre Studies Schools were established – New Rhetoric Studies, English for Specific Purposes, Systemic Functional Linguistics. New Rhetoric Studies is called Rhetorical Genre Studies (RGS) with the term RGS was found by Freedman and increased by Bawarshi and Reiff. The article “Genre as Social Action” by Carolyn Miller the approach to discourse implicit in RGS was mentioned primarily. Miller explicated the importance of the genre for the pedagogical discourse, he stated that the genre is the basic key for comprehending how to react in communicative situation in the academic

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sphere.¹ For instance, academic genres (a seminar, a workshop or a lecture) are often resulted in such a way (linguistically) that help students obtain the specialized knowledge (linguistic forms, terminology, functional language) they acquire in the academic setting with their profession, get prepared for the active participation in the discourse community they will be representing. Miller mentioned to understand the genre as a social action, Berkenkotter and Huckin supposed that the genres “can be changed according to rhetorical circumstances”, “genres evolve, develop and decay”, and in other words, although genres have a certain form, they should not be viewed as static texts as they can be modified depending on the communicative situation.²

Systemic Functional Genre Studies which is famous as The Sydney School based on their theories of the study of the genre on the work Halliday, Halliday and Matthiessen, Halliday and Hasan and Martin who gave the explanation as “the language is as tool for expressing the meaning rather than as a set of rules”. The significance of the meanings in context is clearly explained in the quotation of one of the famous scholars of the SFL approach Halliday who stated that “for a linguist, to describe language without accounting for text is sterile; to describe text without relating it to language is vacuous.”³ SFL states that language has the systems which can give a choice to the writer/speaker for expressing the meanings. Systemic functional linguistics suppose the meaning as social, and the social meaning influence on linguistic forms and the role of form is to represent a social function.

According to the researches of SFL scholars the genre is comprehend as the following:

- the genre has the social peculiarities because the participants act in genres with other people;
- the genre is goal-oriented because the participants use genres to get a particular aim;
- the genre is staged because the participants get their intention with step in communicative situation.⁴

The English for Specific Purpose (ESP) Genre Theory has researched genres according to the comprehending of how language is structured to get the goals in the specific context of use. The theory has been received with great interest by language teachers because of the increasing number of culturally and linguistically diverse students. The term ‘genre’ was represented in ESP by Tarone and her colleagues in 1981. The research interest was the non – native speaker’s language in the spoken and written language form in the academic and professional sphere.

According to the Swales who is the well-known scholar in ESP the genre analysis has two key features: 1) devoting to academic and research English; 2) usage of genre analysis for applied ends. The scientist Swales paid his attention to the quantitative studies the language registers. He paid attention to the identifying of the linguistic features which are connected with the occurrence in a particular linguistic register.⁵ The scientists of the linguistic sphere mentioned

¹ Valerija Malavska. Genre of an Academic Lecture // Turība University, University of Latvia, Latvia LLCE, 2016 3(2), ISSN 2453-7101 - P 57.

² Valerija Malavska. op.cit. - P 57.

³ Valerija Malavska. op.cit. - P 57.

⁴ Valerija Malavska. Genre of an Academic Lecture // Turība University, University of Latvia, Latvia LLCE, 2016 3(2), ISSN 2453-7101 - P 57.

⁵ Valerija Malavska. op.cit. - P 58.

that the genre is the communicative events which has the communicative aims. These communicative aims occur in the particular structure, style, content, and with the intended audience. The specific communicative aims are set by the discourse community – the members of the discourse who provide the discourse content and the genre’s purpose. The discourse community is the people who share the specific aims for the communication, for example, the lecturers and the students who attend lectures. The scientist Swales’s approach was used by the scholar Flowerdew in pedagogy for analyzing of the genre. He mentioned the six features of the discourse communities: 1) common public aims – the participants’ common purpose, for example, the common aim of the lecturer and the student is to exchange new knowledge; 2) The intercommunication’s mechanisms among the participants, for example, lecture room and seminar classroom. 3) The experience and the language competence of the lecturers and the students; 4) The occurrence of the communicative aims in the discourse community is related one or more genres, for example, the lectures of the finance is comprehended by the students of the financial sphere rather than the students of the medicine and the medicine discourse and the medicine lecture will not be comprehended by the students of the finance. 5) The lexis of the discourse community, for example, the pedagogical discourse has its own terminology, abbreviations as well as the medicine discourse has its own terminology. 6) The participants of the discourse community have the relevant knowledge and experience of the discourse content. The purpose of the expert lecturer is to share knowledge to the audience/ students who is belongs to this discourse sphere.¹

According to scholar Bawarshi these three genre schools considered that the analyzing of the genre is connected with discourse community and the purpose of the discourse community’s members which are the main recourse of the genre’s designing for the achieving of the discourse communicative aims.² The analysis of the discourse genre is characterized by the genre’s organization – its structure and its linguistic peculiarities as style, tone, voice, grammar, syntax. All the research schools of the genre mentioned that the genre is a social action which is oriented to the addressee.

Table 2. Some Example of Academic discourse’s Genres.

Genre/Communicative purpose	Register	Style
Academic lecture – to explain new knowledge to the students.	Field/ -lecture room Tenor -lecturer, student Mode -spoken interaction or written text in the PPT	Monological style – one way interaction, the individual style of the lecture, use of the PPT
Seminar – to discuss and improve the knowledge of the student in a particular subject	Field – seminar room Tenor – seminar teacher and student Mode -spoken interaction	Interactive style – the students act in the communicative process, use of the PPT and the individual style of the speakers.
Conference – to exchange knowledge and new ideas	Field – Conference room Tenor – Academic staff Mode – Spoken interaction or written text in PPT	Presentation in a form PPT and the individual style form of the speaker.
Textbook	Field – the subject in Pedagogy Tenor – Academic staff, the students form the academic community Mode – written text	Individual style of the writer.

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² Valerija Malavska.op.cit.- P 60.

This table illustrates the genre, the register and the mode of the academic discourse.¹ The academic lecture is an example for oral academic genre and the scholars of the genre research state that the lecture is the genre of the pedagogical discourse, it is realized through the pedagogical register. In the academic lecture the conceptuality, situationally, improvisation play the great role.

The main features of the academic discourse in the lecture can be:

- The speech should be logical and clear;
- The speech should be in the standard type and the lecturer can use clichéd phrases;
- The speech should be objective and unambiguous;
- The speech of the lecturer should be laconic;
- The speech should have intellectual expressivity.

3. Conclusion. It is important to say that the lecture is as a form of the academic discourse's genre is changeable, because firstly, it formed in the form "chalk and talk" in the pedagogical discourse for the transmission of the knowledge and at present time the lecture includes the active educator who is organized interactive lecture and the new technology which is the main tool of the exchanging knowledge in the educational sphere.

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